

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF USING WHATSAPP ON REDUCTION OF STRESS

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Abstract:

In this current scenario where everyone is busy in their Schedule, they often don't get time for their relatives, friends and family. But thanks to the technology that it helps to cut the distance between our relatives. If they want to talk with their loved ones they like to prefer chat on several applications which free of cost and just required minimum amount of internet package which makes life easier rather to pay high cost of calls and messages to telecom companies. There are number of applications available in the market which people use according to their preference, Whatsapp application is one of them, an application which not only has function of chatting but also other very convenient functions. The main objectives of the study is to identify the using Whatsapp faced on reduction stress. The study was conducted on 400 questionnaire using convenience sampling method. The study makes use of statistical techniques such as simple percentage analysis and Chi- square test in analyzing the data for finding the result. The results revealed that the social media application needs to improve their services to satisfy all types of users. Whatsapp is a great application that offers various benefits to the customer. It provides the best features that an internet messaging application can provide to us. With that, we can easily send enough unrestricted messages to our Whatsapp friends.

Key Words: Whatsapp, Messages & Social media

Introduction:

The application was created in 2009 by Jan Koum and Brian Acton, two former employees of the IT company .Initially, the application was developed for iOS, and then spread across all major smartphone operating systems. Whatsapp uses a modified version of the standard messaging protocol XMPP. And then the entire section is loaded into this central database after installation, an account based on the phone number of the device is created Whatsapp, allowing an end user to provide a list of contacts who, like him, has installed the application.

Whatsapp is a property Facebook.inc application based on multi-platform instant messaging for smartphones. Besides the exchange of text messages, you can call, send images, videos, audio files, share your location (by using integrated in the device maps) and make VoIP calls to anyone with a smartphone equipped with Internet connection that has the application installed.

Using the application is free for the first year after installation, after which you have to subscribe pursuant to tariffs available. The service is activated by the user number, you can switch freely between phone and reinstall or upgrade the software as long as the phone Whatsapp is available for iOS, Android, BlackBerry OS, Series 40, Nokia Symbian and Windows Phone number remains the same..

In addition to text instant messaging, which is the basic function of the application, users Whatsapp can create chat groups, where whenever someone writes a message is seen by everyone in the group (up to 100 participants), share photos , videos, audio files, contacts, and data on the geographic location using Google Maps. As

announced in 2014, from March 2015, with the new update, VoIP calls are included in the functions of the application.

A known issue respect to Whatsapp privacy, is the fact that Whatsapp requires its users send all their contacts to the application server, so you can connect with others just only using the contacts application. While this method is very fast and useful, knowing that its contact is established application sharing, while providing a copy of our data replicated on the servers of the company, including those who do not make use of it is not a subject to leave the planet without firing a heated argument. In theory, the operation makes the information on the phone numbers are stored using hash and not providing other information that can identify you, such as name and surname The March 31, 2013, the Telecommunications Authority in Saudi Arabia, Communications and Information Technology Commission (CITC), has issued a statement regarding the possible restrictive measures against Whatsapp, and other applications like Skype and Viber, invitation providers of these services to adapt to the rules of his country, in relation to monitoring and privacy.

Review of Literature:

Anand Y. Kenchakkanavar and Dr.Gururaj S. Hadagali (2015), made a study on "Use of whatsapp among the Research Scholars of Karnatak University, Dharwad". The main objective of the study is to examine the use of Whatsapp by the social science research scholars of the Karnatak University, Dharwad. A structure questionnaire was designed for the purpose and distributed to 145 regular research scholars, out of which, 139 duly filled in questionnaires were received back with a response rate of 95.86 percent. The collected data were analysed using statistical methods like simple percentage. The results of the study show that a majority of the research scholars are aware of SNSs especially Facebook, Google+ and You Tube and use these SNSs to stay in touch with their friends. It can be indicated from the study that majority, i.e.96.87% research scholars use Whatsapp to participate in group discussion on their research work and to share potos and information on workshops/seminars/conferences.

Alhassan Munkail and Abukari Iddrisu (2015), in their study on "The Impact of social Network Sites on the Academic Performance of Students in the Polytechnics of Ghana". The objective of the study was to investigate the effects of the use of social media on academic performance of students. Whether positive or negative. Obviously a total simple of 600 was drwan out of a total population of 6000 which is a representative of the population. The data were analysed using both Excel and SPSS. Some variables were cross tabulated to examine the correlation or the difference between those variables. This study recommended that even though students geneally use social media for academic purposes, they also use it for non - academic matters. Students should be enouraged to spend more time o ther social media interactions on academic issues rathar than non academic matters.

Dr. Abdullah and F. Al-Daboubi (2014), made study on "The Impact of Social Networking Sites on Applied Science University Students". The intensive use of S.N.S. by great number of people, especially youths and university students, and its impacts on thosse users motivated the researcher to conduct this study. The study random simple consisted of 332 students fro ASU, from both genders, various study levels, specialties. Statistical tolos such as Percentage Analysis, Chi-square Test and Weighted Score Analysis were applied to interpret the data to draw meaningful inferences. The results of the study showed that (133) students out of (332) spent (2 to 3) hours per day as a high average of use.

Ms. Jisha K and Dr. Jebakumar (2014), in their study on "Whatsapp: A Trend Setter in Mobile Communication among Chennai Youth". The main objectives of the study is to examines the usage of whatsapp mobile application among the youth in Chennai región. The study uses online survey method and is restricted to youngsters in Chennai region. Questionnaire was distributed to 100 college students in the age group of 18-23. Random sampling technique was applied and statistical tolols like Percentage Analysis and Chi – Square were carried out to analyse the data and draw interpretation. The study concluded that all the respondents agreed that they are using whatsapp for communication with their friends. They also Exchange images, audio and video files with their friends using whatsapp. It was also proved that the only application that the youth uses when they are spending time on their Smart pone is whatsapp.

Ghulam Shabir et all (2014), in their study on "The Impact of Social Media on Youth: A Case Study of Bahawalpur City". The main objectives of the study is to evaluate the attitude of youth towards social media and measure the spending time on social media. A simple of 300 youngsters was selected and non e random sampling method was used to select the sample from all over population among youth including male and female in Bahawalpur City. Statistical package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for the data analysis and interpreted. Findings show that the majority of the respondents show the agreements with these influences of social media. Respondents opine Face book as their favorite social media form, and then the like Skype as second popular form of social media, the primary place for them, 46 percent responded connect social media in educational institution computer labs, mainstream responded as informative links share, respondents face main problema during use of social media are unwanted messeges, social media is beneficial for youth in the field of education. Social media deteriorating social norms, social media is affecting negatively on study of youth.

Dr. Sankar Kumar Chakraborty (2015), carried out a study entitled, "Impact of Social Media / Social Networks on Education and life of Undergraduate level students of Karimganj town-A survey Sudipta Deb Roy". The main objectives of the study is to find out the positive impact of social media on Education of undergraduate level students. The study was conducted through descriptive survey method of research. The study was conducted on sample of 60 undergraduate students. Simple statistical methods were applied to investigate and analysis the collected data. Simple percentage method was employed to arrive at the results and findings of the data analysis which is graphically shown by Bar Graph and Pie Chart. The Study reveals that, Facebook is the most popular sites among the youths. It provides individuals with a way of maintaining and strengthening social ties which can be beneficial to both social and academic settings.

Parvathy J. and Suchithra R. (2015), in their study, "Impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Youth". The main focus of this study is to present an insight into impact of SNS usage on the minds of youth population. Data collected from 150 respondents through structured questionnaire. Non Probabilistic method of sample selection will be used for this study convenience sampling technique. This study concluded that every technology has its positives and negatives and people who are using has to extra cautious in using them and requested only use them for good cause.

M. Owusu-Acheaw and Agatha Gifty Larson (2015), in their study entitled, "Use of Social Media and its Impact on Academic Performance of Tertiary Institution Students: A Study of Students of Koforidua Polytechnic, Ghana". The main objectives of the study is to identify the benefits obtained from using the social media. The sample

size is 200 people. After the collection of data, the results were analyzed with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and the result shown in tables with corresponding frequencies and percentage. The study revealed that majority of the respondents had mobile phones with internet facility and had knowledge of the existence of social media sites. As a result they visit their social media sites and spend between thirty minutes to three hours every day. In addition, the study revealed that the use of social media had affected academic performance of the respondents negatively and further confirmed that there was a strong positive relationship between the use of social media and academic performance.

Said Fathy El Said Abdul Fattah (2015), carried out a study entitled, "The Effectiveness of Using WhatsApp Messenger as One of Mobile Learning Techniques to Develop Students' Writing Skills". The purpose of this research is to study the effectiveness of using WhatsApp Messenger as one of mobile learning Techniques to develop students' writing skills. The quasi-experimental design was used in this study. Statistical tools such as percentage Analysis and Chi-square Test were applied to interpret the data to draw meaningful inferences. Based on the findings above, WhatsApp technology can also enhance students' active participation in the EFL classroom.

Saleh Ibrahim Alsanie (2015), in their study focused, "Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp) Used, and its Relationship with the University Students Contact with their Families in Saudi Arabia". The aim of the research to study the relationship of the use of social media the following social media: WhatsApp, Twitter and Facebook, continuing university students with their families. Total sample 658 students. The tools used in this study are ANNOVA and correlation. The study recommends the inclusion of these means in a curriculum that is taught to students and explain how to take advantage of them positive, especially in the educational process, and how to avoid Alsalbeh effects associated with their use.

Statement of the Problem:

The Whatsapp server status could either be up, down or running very slow indeed. When this occurs users are not very happy at all and need a platform to say how they are feeling or to ask questions, hopefully we can provide that community. Whatsapp problems can be worldwide, but majority of the time they are more resolute on individual platforms or countries. Some of the main Whatsapp issues that arise is when the service goes down completely. Other noted complaints include people trying to download Whatsapp for Android, iPhone, Mac and more. As well as sign in / log in errors, messages and photos not being sent or received.

Whenever a user installs this app, the app ask the user to enter the respective phone number for verification. If you're unable to complete this verification process you can't use this IM app. User can bypass this verification either through SMS or Voice call verification. There can be various reasons behind the failure of the phone number verification. The first thing you need to check if there is proper connection of the network provider. Secondly, try the voice call verification if SMS isn't reaching your end.

Scope of the Study:

Whatsapp as a separate service, just as it did with Instagram, which it bought for about \$715.3 million in two years ago. The deal provides Facebook entree to new users, including teens who eschew the mainstream social networks but prefer Whatsapp and rivals, which have exploded in size as private messaging takes off. Whatsapp instant messaging facilitates online collaboration and cooperation between online students connected from school or home in a blended mobile lecture. Whatsapp is a free

application that is easy to use. Groups connected to Whatsapp instant massaging can share learning objects easily through comments, texting and messaging. Whatsapp provides students with the ability to create a class publication and thereby publish their work in the group. Information and knowledge are easily constructed and shared through Whatsapp messaging.

Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of the study are:

- ✓ To identify the using of whatsapp faced on reduction of stress.
- ✓ To know usage pattern of whatsapp
- ✓ To know the various opinion of usage of whatsapp.
- ✓ To study the impact of whatsapp.

Research Methodology:

The idea behind this particular section is to reveal the rationale for the research methodology, the method and strategy adopted in collecting data for the research. This part also seeks to reveal how the researchers conducted the research to be able to investigate the impact of whatsapp using on reduction of stress performance of Pubic.

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problems. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. It includes the overall research design, the sampling procedure, data collection method and analysis procedure.

Sampling Design:

A sampling design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy procedure. The sampling design used in this study was descriptive sampling design. It includes surveys and fact finding enquiries of different kinds. The main characterstic of this method is that the researcher has no control over the variables the researcher can report only what has happen end or what is happening. The researcher used this sampling design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about satisfaction of public.

Sampling Method:

The sampling used for the study is convenient sampling .This sampling is selected by the researcher for the purpose of convenience to access. A pilot study is conducted to validate the questionnaire and to confirm the feasibility of the study. Based on the pilot study, the questionnaire is modified suitably to elicit response from the sample group.

Sampling Size:

The study was conducted on 400 questionnaire using convenience sampling method.

Method of Data Collection:

The data for this study are two types: (i) Primary data (ii) Secondary data

Primary Data:

Primary data is the data is collected from the respondent for the first time, it is original in nature. For the purpose of collection of primary data, as a well structured questionnaire was framed and filled by the respondents. The questionnaire comprises of close ended as well as open ended questions.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data are collected from books, web sites etc., and both open ended & close ended questions are incorporated in the questionnaire for the collection of data.

Framework of Analysis:

The following analysis tools used in the study

- ✓ Percentage Analysis
- ✓ Chi – square test

Percentage Analysis:

Percentage refers to a special kind of ration in making comparison between two or more data and to describe relationships. Percentage can also be used to compare the relative terms in the distribution of two or more sources of data

$$\text{Percentage of Respondents} = \frac{\text{Number of Respondents}}{\text{Total Respondents}} \times 100$$

Chi Square Test:

The chi square test is an important test among the several tests of significance developed by satisfaction. Chi – square, symbolically written χ^2 is a statistical measure used in contexts of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance. By comparing a calculated value with the table value of χ^2 for degrees of freedom at given level of significance. We may either accept or reject the null hypothesis. If the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the value, the null hypothesis is accepted, but if the calculate value is equal or greater than table value the hypothesis is rejected.

The formula applied for Chi – square

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected Frequency

Table 1: Social Economic Profile

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percent
1	Age		
	Below 20 years	188	47
	20 – 35 years	180	45
	35 – 50 years	25	6.25
	Above 50 years	7	1.75
	Total	400	100
2	Residence		
	Urban	91	22.25
	Semi – Urban	84	21
	Rural	225	56.25
	Total	400	100
3	Gender		
	Male	169	42.25
	Female	231	57.75
	Total	400	100
4	Marital Status		
	Married	89	22.25
	Unmarried	311	77.75
	Total	400	100
5	Educational Qualification		
	Upto HSC	50	12.5
	Under Graduate	252	63
	Post Graduate	59	14.75
	Professional	33	8.25
	Others	6	1.5
	Total	400	100

6	Occupation		
	Agriculture	38	9.5
	Business	53	13.25
	Government sector employees	9	2.25
	Private sector employees	55	13.75
	Professional	17	4.25
	Home maker	20	5
	Student	208	52
	Total	400	100
7	Type of family		
	Joint	130	32.5
	Nuclear	270	67.5
	Total	400	100
8	Family Members		
	1 - 3 Members	86	21.5
	3 - 5 Members	258	64.5
	Above 5 Members	56	14
	Total	400	100
9	Annual income		
	Below Rs.50,000	158	39.5
	Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000	161	40.25
	Rs.1,00,000 – 3,00,000	61	15.25
	Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000	20	5
	Total	400	100
10.	Using Whatsapp Offline Mode		
	Yes	131	32.75
	No	269	67.25
	Total	400	100
11	Connected Internet at any Time		
	Yes	146	36.5
	No	254	63.5
	Total	400	100
12	Using Whatsapp in hours per day		
	Less than 1 hour	208	52
	1 to 3 hours	117	29.25
	3 to 5 hours	49	12.25
	More than 5 hours	26	6.5
	Total	400	100
13	Using Whastapp Always Chat		
	Family	45	11.25
	Friends	308	77
	Colleagues	37	9.25
	Business dealers	10	2.5
	Total	400	100
14	Using Mobile Phone		
	Android	327	81.75
	I phone	50	12.5
	Black Berry	23	5.75
	Total	400	100
15	Change Mobile phone		
	Trendiness	149	37.25
	Design	99	24.75
	The applications that other phone doesn't have	112	28
	Easy gaming	40	10
	Total	400	100
16	Using Whatsapp Language		
	Chinese	6	1.5

	English	361	90.25
	Tamil	26	6.5
	Others	7	1.75
	Total	400	100
17	Reason for Whatsapp Using		
	Convenience	80	20
	Free	104	26
	Many friends are using whatsapp	179	44.75
	Others	37	9.25
	Total	400	100
18	Using group chat		
	Yes	280	70
	No	120	30
	Total	400	100
19	Need to use group chat		
	Maintain relationship	277	69.25
	Time pass	123	30.75
	Total	400	100
20	Improving relationship		
	Yes	298	74.5
	No	102	25.5
	Total	400	100
21	Using Whatsapp Disadvantage		
	Low privacy	113	28.25
	Easy to be addicted	213	53.25
	Affecting other ways of communiations	59	14.75
	To rely on whatsapp	15	3.75
	Total	400	100
22	Provide free internet charges		
	Yes	180	45
	No	220	55
	Total	400	100
23	Using Whatsapp Keep Time Manage		
	Yes	210	52.5
	No	190	47.5
	Total	400	100
24	Group Chat		
	Highly satisfied	61	15.25
	Satisfied	230	57.5
	Neither satisfied or dissatisfied	29	7.25
	Dissatisfied	64	16
	Highly dissatisfied	16	4
	Total	400	100
25	Sending message but not reply		
	Excited	45	11.25
	Angry	124	31
	Sad	116	29
	Disappointed	73	18.25
	Others	42	10.5
	Total	400	100
26	Unknown Number Message Reaction		
	Don't reply	137	34.25
	Reply	80	20
	Block the number	148	37
	Waiting	35	8.75
	Total	400	100
27	Relieving stress level		
	Yes	213	53.25

	No Total	187 400	46.75 100
28	Using words or symbols		
	Words	34	8.5
	Symbols	134	33.5
	Both	181	45.25
	No reply Total	51 400	12.75 100
29	Using whatsapp helpful to manage stress level		
	Yes	233	58.25
	No Total	167 400	41.75 100
30	Using whatsapp level of stress		
	High	57	14.25
	Moderate	200	50
	Low Total	143 400	35.75 100
31	Mode of stress reduction		
	Yes	209	52.25
	No Total	191 400	47.75 100
32	Level of satisfaction on reducing stress		
	Highly satisfied	38	9.5
	Satisfied	216	54
	Neither satisfied or Dissatisfied	56	14
	Dissatisfied	66	16.5
	Highly Dissatisfied Total	24 400	6 100
33	Time to watching whatsapp		
	To a very large extent	97	24.25
	To a large extent	121	30.25
	To a small extent	127	31.75
	To a small extent Total	55 400	13.75 100
34	Keeping mobile data any whatsapp message missing		
	Always	84	21
	Periodically	201	50.25
	Not at all Total	115 400	28.75 100
35	Whatsapp affected rest time		
	Strongly Disagree	39	9.75
	Disagree	124	31
	Agree	187	46.75
	Strongly Agree Total	50 400	12.5 100

Chi - Square:

Introduction:

The chi square test is an important test among the several tests of significance developed by satisfaction. Chi-square symbolically written x^2 is a statistical measure used in the contexts of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance. It can also be used to make comparison between theoretical population and actual data when categories are used. In this chapter satisfaction of users is analysed. For that purpose the variables Age, Area of Residence, Gender, Marital Status,

Educational qualification, Occupation, Nature of the family, Members of family and Annual Income are taken and compared with satisfaction level.

Table 2: Demographic Profile and Level of Satisfaction With Using Whatsapp

S.No	Variables	High	Moderate	Low	Total	D.f	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value	Result
1	Age					6	3.397	12.592	Not Significant
	Below 20 years	123	51	14	188				
	20 – 35 years	112	59	9	180				
	35 – 50 years	15	9	1	25				
	Above 50 years	4	3	0	7				
Total	254	122	24	400					
2	Area of Residence					4	0.961	9.488	Not Significant
	Urban	58	27	6	91				
	Semi – Urban	50	28	6	84				
	Rural	146	67	12	225				
Total	254	122	24	400					
3	Gender					2	2.378	5.991	Not Significant
	Male	106	56	7	169				
	Female	148	66	17	231				
Total	254	122	24	400					
4	Marital Status					2	7.094	5.991	Significant
	Married	51	36	2	89				
	Unmarried	203	86	22	311				
Total	254	122	24	400					
5	Educational qualification					8	6.781	15.507	Not Significant
	Upto HSC	36	10	4	50				
	Under Graduate	161	78	13	252				
	Post Graduate	33	20	6	59				
	Professional	20	12	1	33				
	Others	4	2	0	6				
Total	254	122	24	400					
6	Occupation					12	12.186	21.026	Not Significant
	Agriculture								
	Business	19	17	2	38				
	Government sector employees	29	20	4	53				
	Private sector employees	4	5	0	9				
	Professional	38	14	3	55				
	Home maker	13	4	0	17				
	Student	13	6	1	20				
	Total	138	56	14	208				
Total	254	122	24	400					
7	Nature of the family					2	0.018	5.991	Not Significant
	Joint Family	82	40	8	130				
	Nuclear Family	172	82	16	270				
Total	254	122	24	400					
8	Members of family					4	1.973	9.488	Not Significant
	1 – 3 Members	50	29	7	86				
	3 – 5 Members	166	78	14	258				
	Above 5 Members	38	15	3	56				
Total	254	122	24	400					
9	Annual Income					6	12.738	12.592	Significant
	Below Rs.50,000	104	49	5	158				
	Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000	106	41	14	161				
	Rs.1,00,000 – 3,00,000	35	24	2	61				
	Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000	9	8	3	20				
Total	254	122	24	400					

However, as the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table at five per cent level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is concluded that there is a significant association between marital status and annual income of the respondents and level of satisfaction towards using Whatsapp.

Table 3: Demographic Profile and Level of Stress Reduced Using Whatsapp

S.No	Variables	High	Moderate	Low	Total	D.f	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table value	Result
1	Age Below 20 years 20 – 35 years 35 – 50 years Above 50 years Total	25 25 6 1 57	82 109 7 2 200	81 46 12 4 143	188 180 25 7 400	6	20.417	12.592	Significant
2	Area of Residence Urban Semi – Urban Rural Total	16 11 30 57	50 50 100 200	25 23 95 143	91 84 225 400	4	10.304	9.488	Significant
3	Gender Male Female Total	30 27 57	84 116 200	55 88 143	169 231 400	2	3.364	5.991	Not Significant
4	Marital Status Married Unmarried Total	18 39 57	41 159 200	30 113 143	89 311 400	2	3.355	5.991	Not Significant
5	Educational qualification Upto HSC Under Graduate Post Graduate Professional Others Total	5 38 9 4 1 57	25 120 34 20 1 200	20 94 16 9 4 143	50 252 59 33 6 400	8	7.894	15.507	Not Significant
6	Occupation Agriculture Business Government sector employees Private sector employees Professional Home maker Student Total	7 14 0 8 2 6 20 57	17 24 5 32 4 10 108 200	14 15 4 15 11 4 80 143	38 53 9 55 17 20 208 400	12	25.653	21.026	Significant
7	Nature of the family Joint Family Nuclear Family Total	28 29 57	54 146 200	48 95 143	130 270 400	2	10.012	5.991	Significant
8	Members of family 1 – 3 Members 3 – 5 Members Above 5 Members Total	15 35 7 57	46 127 27 200	25 96 22 143	86 258 56 400	4	2.519	9.488	Not Significant
9	Annual Income Below Rs.50,000 Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000 Rs.1,00,000 – 3,00,000 Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000 Total	17 20 17 3 57	74 90 24 12 200	67 51 20 5 143	158 161 61 20 400	6	16.399	12.592	Significant

However, as the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table at five per cent level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is concluded that there is a significant association between age, area of residence, occupation, nature of family and annual income of the respondents and level of stress reduced using whatsapp.

Findings:

Chi-Square Test:

Variables Associated With Satisfaction of Using Whatsapp:

- ✓ There is no significant association between age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.

- ✓ There is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is a significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is no significant association between educational qualification of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between members of family of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.

Variables Associated With Stress Reduced Using Whatsapp:

- ✓ There is a significant association between age of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is a significant association between age of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is no significant association between educational qualification of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is a significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is a significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is no significant association between members of family of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ There is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of stress. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected.

Suggestions:

Based upon the study conducted, the following are the suggestions made for better service offered by the social media applications.

- ✓ The study shows that Whatsapp is the most used App amongst information sharing apps like Facebook, We Chat.
- ✓ Whatsapp is a great application that offers various benefits to the customer. It provides the best features that an internet messaging application can provide to us. With that, we can easily send enough unrestricted messages to our Whatsapp friends.
- ✓ The other information sharing apps can speed up their service. Also can make a collaboration with companies and offer a free hours to the users. Many extra features such as voice chat, video chat, etc., can be offered as in whatapp and facebook.

- ✓ Whatsapp could have been even better, if the app would have provided with the facility to send unlimited messages throughout the country or world for free to any number.
- ✓ Most of the respondents prefer whatsapp followed by facebook. The other information sharing app comes back is Hike. The reason is storage space (Mb of the app), speed and popularity.

Conclusion:

The study focuses on consumer aspects of whatsapp in terms of their satisfaction with the use of the information sharing apps. In the study, most respondents are satisfied with the use of information sharing apps. Consumer's satisfaction is affected by factors such as needs fulfilment, performance improvement, ease of use, security/privacy, and influence of the peer. It shows that users of Whatsapp are satisfied with Whatsapp so they will suggest any body for using Whatsapp. The results revealed that the social media application needs to improve their services to satisfy all types of users. The customization of services is needed by the social media application to improve the satisfaction level of all category users. Social media application should take steps to reduce the risk involved in social media application services. So that the users feel social media application services are safe and secure.

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